

Pose Annotation Project for Artworks: A participatory annotation platform for automated body pose estimation in art.

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Context

Many projects in the domain of digital humanities have shown a growing interest for object recognition in artworks (Milani and Fraternali 2020), and, more specifically, for the task of Human Pose Estimation (HPE) (Marsocci and Lastilla 2021; Impett and Süssstrunk 2016; Madhu et al. 2022). HPE is a well defined challenge in computer vision and benefits from large training datasets of annotated images (Lin et al. 2014; Andriluka et al. 2014) that allow the creation of highly performative machine learning models (Cao et al. 2021; Girshick 2015; Redmon et al. 2016). However, these datasets are usually made of recent photographs collected in the web, capturing a loose western perspective with all its biases. Moreover, their content diverges from artworks created in past Centuries. For the case of figurative paintings, visual features, such as brush marks and color shades, but also the morphology of bodies, dressing codes or the overall composition, have an impact on the accuracy of HPE models. These many differences do not enable the field of digital art history to fully benefit from the performance of existing models and the lack of a proper training dataset for artworks makes it difficult to retrain them. Therefore, we present the Pose Annotation Project for Artworks (PAPA), which goal is to produce a training dataset for body pose estimation on artworks through a platform for participatory annotations of images.

A platform to annotate images

In order to align with standards and to ease the use of the dataset with existing machine learning models, the annotation format proposed by the Microsoft Common Objects in COntext dataset (COCO) (Lin et al. 2014) is used. The format includes body recognition via segmentation, bounding boxes and keypoints annotations, which are stored using JSON. The total of 17 keypoints correspond to the coordinates of the nose, eyes, ears, shoulders, elbows, wrists, hips, knees and ankles for each body present on an image.

Figure 1 – Three different annotation tasks

Based on this standard format and on collected testimonies from similar projects (Hervy et al. 2019; Simpson, Page, and De Roure 2014), it was decided to decompose the annotation task into three subtasks to ease the work of participants and foster more engagement from their part. The three different tasks are the following:

1. segmentation of the bodies
2. keypoints annotation
3. correction of the annotations

A similar layout is used for each task, where the image to be annotated is on the center and a toolbox on the right hand side of the screen. The toolbox holds a list with information on the current status of the annotations for the image (see figure 1).

For the segmentation task (1), participants have to draw the contours of each body present on the image and save them individually in the list of the toolbox, where it can be selected, saved or removed if needed. An *undo* and *clear* button are also available to perform changes. Based on these different segmentations, a bounding box is then automatically generated around the different segmented objects.

Regarding the second task (2), a masked image based on the bounding box of a segmented figure is displayed, thus showing one body at a time. On the right hand side, a list of the different

body keypoints which can be selected one after another and placed on the figure with the help of the cursor.

For the last task (3), the participants are presented with a fully annotated figure. If the annotation does not seem correct, then the participants have the possibility to perform changes with the help of an eraser and pen tool, as well as a repositioning of the keypoints.

Future developments

For the current implementation of the platform, the dataset used consists of a total of 5'240 paintings from the digitized collection of the Fototeca from the Bibliotheca Hertziana. Dating mostly from the early modern time, the figurative content of the images aim to ease the task for a first series of annotations and to open the discussion on the complexity of artworks annotations and the possible extension of the dataset to other artwork types and epochs. Indeed, with the need to recognize bodies in art comes the question of the border between figurative and abstract representation, and the limit for such a project. Furthermore, the platform itself and annotation process will be assessed and potentially enhanced from this first trial.

Acknowledgement

Many thanks to Mr Josip Harambasic for his collaboration on the implementation of the platform.

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